

SZ-SB-III-01-02 Networking among teachers from different schools (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090506
ID	SZ-SB-III-01-02
Title	Networking among teachers from different schools
Educational area	#school
Persona	P: Selin - Teacher https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091270
Short description	Teacher Selin would like to network with other teachers to exchange ideas about art classes.
Result	Selin finds a teacher to exchange ideas with and arranges to chat.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Process "Teacher networks with teacher from another school"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Selin is registered at BIRD• Selin is logged in to BIRD
Components	#buddyfinder #learningpathfinder #workspace #chat
Services / tools	#video-conference

Problem scenario

Introduction

Selin Sonntag has been assigned to substitute art teaching in a 6th-grade class at her comprehensive school for the next few months. Art is outside her area of expertise and she doesn't have access to teaching templates or materials. She is looking for information and exchange opportunities to prepare and conduct the lessons in the best possible way.

Problem definition

Selin needs information about requirements and materials to plan her sixth-grade art class. She also wants to talk to other art teachers, as there are no art teachers at her school she could ask for support.

Background and context

The teacher shortage, increased workload, and colleagues acute illnesses mean that teachers like Selin often have to teach outside their own disciplines. Selin aims to inspire a love of art, build fine motor skills, foster tolerance for mistakes and create a safe space for children to grow. Group projects are very suitable for these goals, but they not only need to be carefully planned, but also require a lot of materials and tools. Selin simply lacks the experience to best implement these things specifically in art classes.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Selin prefers to make her lessons interactive and experiential. It's important to her that topics and learning or media offerings are appropriate to the situation and the students. Selin mostly teaches higher grades and has to rethink her work a bit in order to create age-appropriate spaces for the 6th grade students to try things out and get hands-on experience. Selin is open to new things and willing to experiment. When it comes to art, she simply lacks the experience and craves interaction with trained art teachers.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Selin has already looked at the websites of some of the schools with an artistic profile in her area and found some great ideas. Now the question is how to contact the responsible teachers. Since their contact details are not provided on the respective websites, inquiries must be directed to the school office or administration. This process is too complicated and also wastes valuable time.

Activity scenario

Process "Teacher networks with teacher from another school"

Step 1: Selin opens BIRD and navigates to the LearningPathFinder to search for suitable materials and information.

Step 2: She enters the following keywords into the Learningpathfinder search: "art class" and "6th grade." After submitting the search query, she is presented with a long list of results that seems overwhelming at first glance.

Step 3: BIRD offers a tooltip that allows students to connect with another teacher who has the "6th Grade Art Class" project in their profile. For this purpose, the Buddyfinder is suggested, which she can access either directly from the LearningPathFinder or find the portlet in the navigation.

Step 4: Selin likes this suggestion because it's easier to talk to another teacher instead of browsing through dozens of websites. She switches directly from the Learning Pathfinder to the Buddyfinder.

Step 5: Selin provides the following information that she considers important for her search:

- State: Open
- City: Open
- School Type: Open
- Subject: Art
- Grade: Lower School
- Aim: Exchange, collaborative lesson planning, competency-based instruction, 6th grade
- Gender: Open
- Group or Individual: Individual

She submits her search.

Step 6: She receives a notification in BIRD and on her networked work email address that the Buddyfinder has found some suitable teachers who would like to network on the topics mentioned.

Step 7: Selin looks at the potential buddies and sends a contact request. In the free text field, she briefly explains her request to the teacher she has chosen.

Step 8: The teacher Selin contacted receives the request and confirms it.

Step 8: Once Selin's request is confirmed, the chat opens.

Step 10: Selin first introduces herself to the other teacher and explains her current situation again, going into more detail.

Step 11: The other teacher responds to Selin by introducing herself as well. They both agree that it's easier to talk about this topic rather than just texting, so they schedule a meeting via video conferencing.